

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CORE-SHELL TYPE P3HT@PEO COMPOSITE NANOFIBERS USING SINGLE NOZZLE SYSTEM

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Keywords: *P3HT@PEO composite, Electrospinning, Single Nozzle, Nanofiber*

Abstract

Poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) and polyethylene oxide (PEO) composite nanofibers (denoted P3HT@PEO fiber) were prepared using an electrospinning apparatus equipped with a single nozzle and its structure was characterized. It is found that P3HT locates in the core while PEO in the shell of the composite fiber. This kind of core-shell structure was found to originate from the viscosity difference and shear flow during electrospinning process.

1 Introduction

Electrospinning is a facile method for fabricating various materials into nanofibers over a large area. Electrospun polymer, metal oxide and metal nanofibers have been widely used in biomedical, environmental, and electrical applications. In the case of electrospun P3HT fibers many research groups applied the fibers to organic thin film transistors (OTFTs). [1, 2] However due to its large diameter its application to organic photovoltaic (OPV) cells as an active material is yet impossible although P3HT polymer itself is widely used.

To fabricate P3HT nanofibers with sub 100 nm in diameter a dual nozzle system has been typically adopted in an electrospinning apparatus. However, adopting a dual nozzle system requires somewhat complicated experimental conditions because the fiber morphology is changed by a small variation for example in the distance between outer and inner nozzles. [3] Herein we tried to fabricate P3HT/PEO composite nanofibers that will subsequently yield P3HT nanofibers with the diameter of hopefully sub 100 nm after removal of PEO. Since a single nozzle

is adopted P3HT should locate in the core of the composite nanofibers consisting of P3HT and PEO to get such thin nanofibers. It was thus focused on elucidating a core/shell type structure-evolution mechanism operating during the composite fiber formation.

2 Experimental

Electrospinning dope solution was prepared by dissolving both P3HT and an auxiliary polymer, PEO, in chloroform and polar solvent mixture at 50 °C. A metal needle (gauge no. 28) was used as for an electrospinning nozzle. The electro-spinner was set with the distance of 21 cm from the nozzle to a grounded collector plate and the bias voltage of 23 kV to the metal needle. The spinning dope solution was fed with a rate of 1.0 ml/h in air atmosphere at 25~26 °C and 19~21 % relative humidity.

The morphology of the P3HT@PEO composite nanofibers were examined under a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM; JEOL JSM-6330F), operating at 5 kV accelerating voltage. The chemical analysis of the P3HT@PEO composite nanofibers were characterized by transmission electron microscope (TEM; Tecnai F20) operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV equipped with energy dispersion spectroscopy (EDS).

3 Results and Discussion

The electrospun P3HT@PEO composite fibers were successfully prepared by electrospinning with conductivity controlled solution. Figure 1 shows that there is no defect over large area (see Fig 1(a)) and

the diameter of an individual fiber has the diameter of approximately 100 nm.

Fig.1. (a) SEM micrographs of homogeneous electrospun P3HT@PEO fibers over large area and (b) a magnified image of (a) with a scale bar of 100 nm.

The structure of the composite fibers could be a core-shell type structure or a randomly phase-separated structure. To see which one is the case, element mapping using EDS was carried out for sulfur and oxygen that are typical elements of P3HT and PEO respectively. Fig. 2 illustrates the scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) image and mapping image of each element. Due to the low melting temperature (70 °C) of PEO, the STEM and EDS analysis was intentionally performed using very thick fiber. Almost all fibers have the diameter no less than 100 nm. The element mapping image clearly shows that sulfur element locates in the core while oxygen at the shell of the composite fibers, indicating the presence of P3HT in the core and PEO at the shell. This type of composite fiber may be favorable for the preparation of very thin nanofibers of conjugated polymers including P3HT.

The core-shell structure formation from a single nozzle system may be unusual. To investigate this core-shell type structure evolution mechanism, the energy dissipation of the fiber was calculated. Energy dissipation rate is given as

$$E \propto \int \eta \left(\frac{dv}{dr} \right)^2 r dr \quad (1)$$

where η is the viscosity, v is the velocity, and r is a radial position from the center in Fig. 3. Basic assumptions of the calculation are similar with a work studied by Williams. [4] To study the energy dissipation rate of the flow, cross section of the flow is divided into three regions. Viscosity of region 2 (dark region) is higher than that of region 1 and 3

(light region). In this system, PEO solution has high viscosity.

Fig.2. (a) STEM micrograph of electrospun P3HT@PEO composite fiber and (b) EDS mapping with the intensity graph on the selected area of (a).

Fig. 3. Schematic image of the flow model.
Region 1 and 3 have low viscosity η_1 , and
region 2 has high viscosity η_2 .

System of the electrostatic flow is different from laminar flow due to the surface charge of the flow. Tangential stress at the surface is generated by the surface charge, so the surface velocity (velocity of the region 3) is always larger than the velocity at the center (velocity of the region 1). [5] To simplify the calculation, the relative velocity at the center is fixed as 0, and the stress profile is assumed to be linear. The velocity profiles of each region are calculated based on integration,

$$v_1 = \frac{Kr^2}{2\eta_1} \quad (2-1)$$

$$v_2 = \frac{K}{2\eta_1}(Hr^2 + (1-H)r_1^2) \quad (2-2)$$

$$v_3 = \frac{K}{2\eta_1}(r^2 - (1-H)(r_2^2 - r_1^2)) \quad (2-3)$$

where K is a constant related to the stress profile, $H = \eta_1/\eta_2$. According to Eq. (1), the energy dissipation rate can be obtained.

$$E_1 = \frac{K^2 r_1^4}{4\eta_1} \quad (3-1)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{K^2 H}{4\eta_1}(r_2^4 - r_1^4) \quad (3-2)$$

$$E_3 = \frac{K^2}{4\eta_1}(1^4 - r_2^4) \quad (3-3)$$

$$E = \sum E_1 + E_2 + E_3 \\ = \frac{K^2}{4\eta_1}(1^4 - (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4)) \quad (4)$$

If the flow consists of one phase, the energy dissipation rate is

$$E_{\text{homoo}} = \frac{K_{\text{homoo}}^2}{4\eta_1} \quad (5)$$

Therefore,

$$\therefore \frac{E}{E_{\text{homoo}}} = \frac{K^2}{K_{\text{homoo}}^2}(1 - (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4)) \quad (6)$$

Volumetric flow rate of two phases and one phase should be same, so

$$Q = \int 2\pi v r dr \quad (7)$$

$$Q_1 = \frac{K\pi}{4\eta_1} r_1^4 \quad (8-1)$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{K\pi}{4\eta_1}(H(r_2^4 - r_1^4) \\ + 2(1-H)(r_1^2 r_2^2 - r_1^4)) \quad (8-2)$$

$$Q_3 = \frac{K\pi}{4\eta_1}(1 + (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4) \\ - 2(1-H)(r_2^2 - r_1^2)) \quad (8-3)$$

$$Q = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 = Q_{\text{homoo}} = \frac{K_{\text{homoo}}\pi}{4\eta_1} \quad (9)$$

From the equation (8) and (9),

$$\therefore \frac{K}{K_{\text{homoo}}} = \frac{1}{1 + (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4) - 2(1-H)(r_2^2 - r_1^2)} \quad (10)$$

Therefore,

$$\therefore \frac{E}{E_{\text{homoo}}} = \frac{1 - (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4)}{(1 + (1-H)(r_2^4 - r_1^4) - 2(1-H)(r_2^2 - r_1^2))^2} \quad (11)$$

The calculation result demonstrates that low viscosity core flow has lower energy state compared to high viscosity core flow. Since P3HT has lower viscosity compared to PEO in chloroform, the P3HT migrated to the core region of the P3HT@PEO composite nanofibers.

3 Conclusions

In this study, P3HT@PEO nanofibers were successfully electrospun and the structure was investigated in detail. The core-shell nanostructure could be simply obtained using a single nozzle system, and the core part and shell part are determined by the viscosity difference between the two polymer materials.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korea government (MEST) [No.2010-0029244].

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